

Ball Bearing Fault Detection with Speed and Load

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Abstract -- Ball bearings are essential components in industrial machinery, and their failure can lead to costly downtime and repairs. Detecting faults in ball bearings early is critical to maintaining the efficiency and safety of machines. This report details the development of a diagnostic app designed to enhance the early detection and management of ball bearing faults. The Ball Bearing Fault Detection App is an advanced tool that supports comprehensive monitoring of bearing health by analyzing speed and load conditions. Key features include real-time vibration analysis, fault type classification, predictive maintenance alerts, and user-friendly data visualization. By providing engineers and maintenance teams with actionable insights, the app enables timely interventions, promotes proactive maintenance, and contributes to optimal machine performance and reduced operational costs.

Keywords: *Early Ball bearing fault detection, Real-time ball bearing monitoring.*

INTRODUCTION

This project focuses on the detection of faults in ball bearings under varying speed and load conditions. Ball bearings are vital components in industrial machinery, enabling smooth rotational motion and reducing friction between moving parts. The health of ball bearings is critical to maintaining optimal machine performance, and early fault detection is

essential to prevent costly downtime and avoid equipment failure. Ball bearing faults, such as inner race faults, outer race faults, and ball defects, can lead to reduced efficiency and severe machinery damage if left undetected.

Common types of faults in ball bearings include defects in the inner and outer races, cage, and rolling elements. These faults can progress rapidly under adverse conditions and may cause significant issues in machinery. Implementing an effective fault detection system is essential, as unexpected bearing failures are costly and can impact safety, especially in high-demand applications. In this project, a diagnostic app has been developed to detect faults in ball bearings based on real-time speed and load data.

The goal of the Ball Bearing Fault Detection App is to provide maintenance teams and engineers with the tools needed to monitor bearing health, diagnose potential issues, and perform timely interventions. By leveraging real-time data, vibration analysis, and fault classification algorithms, the app facilitates proactive maintenance, reduces machine downtime, and optimizes the overall performance and reliability of machinery.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Accurately identifying the presence of a bearing fault can be challenging in practice, especially when the fault is still at its incipient stage and the signal-to-noise ratio of the monitored signal is small. In addition, unlike other motor failures (stator inter-turn, broken rotor bar, etc. [1,2] That can be accurately determined by electric signals, the uniqueness of a bearing failure lies in its multi-physics nature. It is the primary mechanical vibration due to the bearing defect that triggered the abnormal electric signal, which further influences the output torque, the motor speed, and finally the bearing vibration pattern itself, whose fault frequency is directly proportional to the motor speed [3,4].

The accuracy of the traditional physical model-based vibration analysis can be further affected by background noise due to external motion and vibration, and its sensitivity is also subject to change with respect to sensor mounting positions and spatial constraints in a highly-compact environment [5,6]. Therefore, instead of vibration analysis, a popular alternative approach is to analyze the stator current signal which has already been measured in motor drives to regulate the motor's torque and speed, and thus it would not bring extra device or installation costs.

Advantages such as economic savings and simple implementation, the motor current signature analysis (MCSA) can encounter many practical issues [7]. For example, the magnitude of stator currents at the bearing fault frequency can vary at different loads, different speeds, and different power ratings of the motors themselves, thus bringing challenges to identify a universal threshold of the stator current to trigger a fault alarm at an arbitrary operating condition.[8-10] Therefore, a thorough and systematic commissioning stage is usually required while the motor is still at the healthy condition, and the healthy data would be collected while the target motor is running at different loads and speeds.

Most of the challenges described above can be attributed to the fact that all of the conventional model-based methods rely solely upon the threshold value of different signals (data) at the fault frequencies to determine the presence of a bearing

fault [11]. These models can only describe the signal features of a few well-defined fault types, while in reality the naturally occurring faults are often more complicated. For example, at the early stage of a fault the signatures can be less well defined or even not traceable by using the physical models; more than one faults can occur at the same time, which potentially modifies the fault features and creates new features due to the coupling effect [11].

There may exist many unique features or patterns hidden in the data themselves that can potentially reveal a bearing fault, and it is almost impossible for humans to identify these convoluted features through manual observation or interpretation [12]. Therefore, many researchers have applied various machine learning (ML) algorithms, including artificial neural networks (ANN), principal component analysis (PCA), support vector machines (SVM), etc., to parse the data, learn from them, and apply what they have learned to make intelligent decisions regarding the presence of bearing faults [12]. Most of the literature applying these ML algorithms report.

Literature survey incorporates more than 180 papers dedicated to bearing fault diagnosis, around 80 of which employed some type of DL approaches. The number of papers also grows exponentially over the recent years, indicating a booming interest in employing DL methods for bearing fault diagnostics. In this context, this paper seeks to present a thorough overview on the recent research work devoted to applying ML and DL techniques on bearing fault diagnostics [13,14]. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we introduce some of the most popular datasets used for bearing fault detection.

K-nearest neighbors (k-NN), SVM, etc., with a brief overview of major publications applying each ML algorithm for bearing fault detection. For the main part of this paper, in Section IV, we take a deep dive into the research frontier of DL based bearing fault identification [15]. In this section, we will provide our understanding of the research trend toward DL approaches. Specifically, we will discuss the advantages of DL based methods over the conventional ML methods in terms of fault feature extraction and classifier performance, as well as new

functionalities offered by DL techniques that cannot be accomplished before [16,17].

Data is the foundation for all of the ML methods. To develop effective ML and DL algorithms for bearing fault detection, a good collection of datasets is necessary [18]. Since the natural bearing degradation is a gradual process and may take many years, most people conduct experiment and collect data either using bearings with artificially induced faults, or with accelerated life testing methods.

Asymmetries in the system cause the deformation caused by misalignment to be different at each angle of rotation. The 2X harmonic is widely accepted as a main symptom of mis alignment, but the author states that harmonic terms can arise from several different sources. Nader Sawalhi, developed a model to characterize and identify both angular and parallel misalignment from vibration response (displacement). A simulation model of a three-pin-type flexible coupling was presented, and a comparison between the simulated results and those obtained experimentally was presented. The authors reported that the higher the shaft speed, the more important the harmonic amplitude [19,20].

III. METHODOLOGY

The study used a pre trained network is retrained using transfer learning to classify bearing scalogram images. This network training is performed over the online available bearing fault dataset with 10-fold cross-validation.

In the proposed methodology, the trained network is then tested and validated to classify the scalograms obtained for the data acquired from an indigenously designed bearing test rig. During real-time experimentation, the fault diagnosing module generates fault feedback in the form of an audio warning signal and a visual optical flag in the control room of the condition monitoring and maintenance center. When a bearing spins, any defect or irregularities in the raceway surfaces or the rolling elements such as indentation, spalls, crack, flaking or irregularities in roundness of the rolling element excites periodic frequencies called fundamental defect frequencies.

System design flow /Block diagram-

The above block diagram on bearing faults has been made available by the Machinery Failure Prevention Technology (MFPT) society to aid in the study of bearing analysis. This fault dataset consists of two types of NICE bearing faults obtained from the MFPT database, which have flaws of the outer race face, inner race face, and the standard ball bearing data

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+FN+FP+TN} \times 100\%$$

$$Precision, PPV = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \times 100\%$$

$$Recall, Sensitivity, TPR = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \times 100\%$$

$$F_1 \text{ score} = \frac{2 \times TP}{2 \times TP + FP + FN} \times 100\%$$

$$Specificity, TNR = \frac{TN}{FP+TN} \times 100\%$$

The ball pass outer race frequency (BPFO) is the number of occurrences for which a rolling element or ball bearing traverses a specific location at the outer race of the bearing. It is determined with the equation below.

$$BPFO = \frac{nfr}{2} \left(1 - \frac{d}{D} \cos \phi\right)$$

The ball pass inner race frequency (BPFI) is determined using the following relationship. BPFI refers to the number of times a rolling element or ball bearing passes at a specific position at the inner race of the bearing.

$$BPFI = \frac{nfr}{2} \left(1 + \frac{d}{D} \cos \phi\right)$$

where n is the number of rolling elements, f_r is the shaft speed, D is the diameter of the ball bearing, d is the pitch diameter, and ϕ is the bearing angle of contact with the races. ϕ is determined using the Turns method or with the measurement of internal clearance. It is set as 25° by the manufacturer for SKF 6202 bearing.

IV.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This figure illustrates the frequency spectrum analysis of a ball bearing to identify potential faults. The x-axis represents frequency in Hertz (Hz), ranging from 0 to 1400 Hz, which shows the rate of vibration cycles per second. The y-axis displays the magnitude, indicating the intensity of vibration signals at each frequency component. In this analysis, specific peaks in the frequency spectrum correspond to particular vibration patterns associated with different bearing faults.

A key feature of this spectrum is the annotated peak at 103 Hz, marked by an arrow, which highlights an "Outer Race Bearing Fault." This peak has a noticeably higher magnitude than surrounding frequencies, suggesting it is a fault signature specific to the bearing's outer race. In ball bearings, outer race defects produce distinct vibration signals at characteristic frequencies, and the high peak at 103 Hz strongly indicates a defect in this area. By identifying such peaks, this frequency analysis helps in diagnosing bearing faults, allowing for timely intervention and maintenance.

This figure shows a periodogram power spectral density (PSD) estimate for a bearing fault detection analysis. A periodogram is a method used to estimate the power spectrum of a signal, helping to identify prominent frequencies that may indicate faults in machinery. The plot here has "Frequency (kHz)" on the x-axis and "Power/frequency (dB/Hz)" on the y-axis. Peaks in the PSD indicate frequencies where there is significant energy, likely due to mechanical faults.

In this plot, a notable peak is identified at 103 Hz, which is highlighted as an "Outer race Bearing Fault." This implies that the outer race (the outer

ring of the bearing) is likely damaged, generating vibrations at this frequency. The detection of this frequency suggests that a fault may have developed, possibly affecting the bearing's performance and causing abnormal vibrations. Such information is crucial for predictive maintenance, allowing engineers to address faults before they lead to significant equipment failures.

In this figure, the red curve represents the vibration signal of an inner race fault in a bearing, while the blue curve corresponds to the Gaussian function used for signal analysis. The vibration signal appears as oscillatory behavior with spikes, which are typical of fault-related patterns in rotating machinery. The Gaussian function overlays the vibration signal and seems to serve as a reference or a windowing function to focus on specific aspects of the signal, such as fault-induced amplitudes and periodic characteristics.

In this figure, the frequency spectrum of the vibration signal is shown, highlighting the fault-related frequency components. The significant peak at 166.4 Hz corresponds to the Ball Pass Frequency of the Inner race (BPF1), a key characteristic frequency for detecting inner race

faults in bearings. The value of sigma ($\sigma = 3.75$) appears to be a parameter related to the Gaussian envelope or spectral analysis technique used. The graph indicates that the dominant frequency component and its harmonics are directly linked to the fault condition.

This figure depicts the Gaussian-modulated signal in the frequency domain. The red curve likely corresponds to the original signal, while the blue curve represents the Gaussian function applied in the frequency domain. The periodic oscillations of the Gaussian function are visible, aligning with the harmonics of the fault frequencies. The Gaussian modulation may have been used to enhance the visibility of specific frequency bands or isolate fault-related components, making it easier to identify the fault frequency and its harmonics.

In this figure, a frequency spectrum is displayed with the x-axis representing frequency (in Hz) and the y-axis representing amplitude. The spectrum appears to be the result of a Fourier Transform analysis, which breaks down a signal

into its constituent frequencies. A prominent peak can be observed at approximately 99.84 Hz with a corresponding amplitude of 54.43, indicating that this frequency dominates the signal. This peak is highlighted with a data marker, and a legend in the top right notes that this corresponds to "At Sigma=1," with the identified frequency being approximately 99.42 Hz. The presence of other smaller peaks suggests harmonics or additional frequency components within the signal. Overall, the figure likely represents the spectral content of a periodic or oscillatory signal.

The CWT scalogram images hold promising state features embedded into them in terms of absolute continuous wavelet transform bounded with the occurrence time information. The high amplitude spikes in the vibration signal in a particular frequency band can be assessed from the scalogram. The higher CWT magnitude is represented with white spikes in the scalogram image for the entire experimental epoch, as shown in Fig. 3. These increased CWT spikes

represent the bearing fault occurrences in terms of features. While the normal condition does not show a significantly higher magnitude of CWT which is represented in blue color.

V. CONCLUSION

This study examines the non-invasive fault classification technique for ball bearings as rolling elements. The mechanical foundation of rotary machinery is the bearing. Failure of these parts can halt operations and cause financial losses that are significantly greater than the cost of the part itself.

VII. REFERENCES

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